

Effect of Subcutaneous Semaglutide on Diabetic Retinopathy among Adults with Type 2 Diabetes in Saudi Arabia. A Systematic Review

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Abstract

Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is one of the leading causes of progressive and irreversible vision loss. The relationship between metabolic control and progression of DR is observed in previous landmark randomized clinical studies. Moreover, a potential association between DR progression and glucagon-like peptide1 receptor agonists (GLP1-RA) is reported in diabetes literature. **Objectives:** To explore the effect of semaglutide treatment on diabetic retinopathy progression in adults with type 2 diabetes (T2DM) among the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) area. **Methods:** This is a systematic review of randomized clinical trials, we searched electronic databases including Google Scholars, PubMed, Science Direct, Cochrane, ClinicalTrials.gov, and The Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) terms using the PRISMA flow chart based on our inclusion criteria and used PROSPERO for searching for registered systematic reviews in MENA area. **Results:** Among 12 studies 11,854 patients were included in the mean follow-up period which was 52.5 weeks on semaglutide therapy with non-significant association with a pooled effect size for retinopathy incidence of 1.12 (95% CI: 1.00, 1.12). **Conclusion:** The current literature revealed that semaglutide has an uncertain effect on diabetic retinopathy progression. A need for larger randomized clinical trials in MENA area to expose the definitive effect.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease that is associated with microvascular complications such as retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy.

DR is one of the leading causes of progressive and irreversible vision loss [1]. The relationship between metabolic control and progression of DR is observed in

previous landmark randomized clinical studies. The Diabetes Control and Complication Trial (DCCT) and the Epidemiology of Diabetes Interventions and Complications (EDIC) have demonstrated the effectiveness of intensive therapy in reducing the early stages of microvascular disease in type one diabetes [2].

More Information

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vision loss,
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An early worsening of DR has been noticed more in patients who received intensive therapy versus the conventional therapy [2]. Seemingly, similar findings were observed in the early management of type 2 diabetes landmark trials [3]. Multiple factors might explain the progression of DR including long duration of diabetes, poor glycemic control, and poorly controlled hypertension. Rapid improvement in diabetes control has been reported in different studies as one of the possible causes of DR progression [4]. Reviewing multiple new anti-hyperglycemia agents and their effects on the retina have supported the evidence that incretin-based therapy in general is beneficial. However, subcutaneous semaglutide has shown an increase in the progression of DR in patients with pre-existed retina diseases [5]. Cardiovascular outcome trials (CVOTs) have shown that novel anti-hyperglycemia agents such as GLP1-RAs resulted in a significant reduction of CVD morbidity and mortality rates in the type 2 diabetes population as well as the reduction in diabetic nephropathy was noticed, however, the effect on DR was controversial among these trials [6]. SUSTAIN-6 Trial concluded that the use of semaglutide has resulted in a progression of DR in the treatment group [7]. G. Albert et al reviewed in a meta-analysis the adverse effects of GLP1-RA on retinopathy in CVOTs. There was a negative clinical correlation between worsening of retinopathy and greater improvement of HbA1c in a longer duration of the trial. The change in DR was predominantly found only in patients receiving subcutaneous semaglutide for more than one year and decreases in HbA1c greater than 1.0% [8]. Reviewing these studies concluded that the criteria to define new versus worsening retinopathy was not unified in the studies, hence the need for further focused studies to evaluate the unique effect of semaglutide on DR progression is required [8].

A similar negative correlation of HbA1c improvement and worsening of DR with once weekly (OW) subcutaneous semaglutide is discussed in other reviews [9,10]. In a post hoc analysis of SUSTAIN trials to evaluate DR data, an increase in DR progression in patients with pre-existed retinopathy was reported in the SUSTAIN-6 trial is primarily attributable to the magnitude and rapidity of reduction in HbA1c in the early phase of the trial [12]. In the SUSTAIN-6 Trial, a need for interventions such as retinal photocoagulation or treatment with intravitreal agents for vitreous hemorrhage or diabetes-related blindness, that is associated with semaglutide compared to placebo [15]. A further focused look is needed to understand the impact of OW semaglutide on DR and physicians should be alerted about the risk of worsening DR associated with intensified treatment as in the provided information with the use of insulin [12]. A notable variation of GLP1-RA agents on the retina has been

reported in a narrative review of the safety and tolerability of OW GLP1-RA, with exception of semaglutide, other GLP1-RAs have a safe retina profile [16].

A higher incidence of DR progression in the SUSTAIN-6 Trial as previously discussed. Nevertheless, a head-to-head comparison between OW Semaglutide and dulaglutide did not show any difference in the progression of DR [17]. Most of the GLP1-RA human data resulted from CVOTs, retinal changes were not appropriately evaluated. The call for further studies to incorporate DR degree to understand the real impact of such agents on the retina [18]. Experimental studies on animals and human models have reported a positive protective effect of semaglutide on retinal cells from hyperglycemia, hence the noticed results of worsening DR with semaglutide are surprising [13].

Other observations in the use of subcutaneous semaglutide showed a beneficial effect on glaucoma and other neurodegenerative diseases [14]. Due to the lack of RCT that focuses on semaglutide effects on DR as a primary endpoint, a research study to look at how Semaglutide compared to placebo affects diabetic eye disease in people with type 2 diabetes (FOCUS), hopefully, will reveal the mystery of semaglutide effect on DR [19]. GLP1-RA medications are used more frequently than before in the MENA region. In Saudi Arabia, multiple GLP1-RAs are available in the health care system. OW Semaglutide is the most economically and clinically favorable vs other GLP1-RA agents [20,21]. The effect of semaglutide effects on DR is still unclear, especially in MENA area. This systematic review is designed to evaluate the effect of semaglutide use (oral and subcutaneous injections) on DR progression worldwide focusing on MENA area.

Objectives

To explore the effect of semaglutide treatment on diabetic retinopathy outcomes in adults with T2DM patients among MENA area.

Methodology

Study Design

A systematic review of relevant publications on the effects of semaglutide on diabetic retinopathy among adults with type two diabetes in Saudi Arabia. The methodology and results are reported according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) statement for included RCTs.

Data Sources and Searches

Searching electronic databases including PubMed, Google Scholar, Cochrane, and ClinicalTrials.gov for eligible publications.

The Medical Subject Heading (MeSH) terms used in the search process include 'Type 2 diabetes mellitus', 'glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonist' and 'Diabetes retinopathy'. Specific drug agents such as 'semaglutide', 'liraglutide', and 'dulaglutide'. Terms

describes diabetes retinopathy related outcomes such as “retinal photocoagulation”, “Retinal hemorrhages”, “Retina treatment”, “blindness” and “eye disease”. We also performed a supplementary search for eligible publications. This database search was conducted by two independent reviewers (GA), (TH) and referred for third reviewer (KM) and discussion.

We also used the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO) to search for any systematic review in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) area Including these keywords semaglutide and Saudi Arabia, diabetic retinopathy, retinopathy, and Arab countries, Semaglutide and Arabian Gulf countries, Semaglutide and North Africa, Semaglutide and Middle East, Through also searching semaglutide with each country: Algeria, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bahrain, Djibouti, Egypt, Iran, Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Libya, Mauritania, Morocco, Oman, Qatar, Somalia, Palestine, Sudan, Syria, Tunisia, Turkey, United Arab Emirates, Yemen, Western Sahara.

Study Selection

All randomized clinical trials on adults with type 2 diabetes comparing the FDA-approved GLP1-RA with placebo. All randomized clinical trials on GLP-1 receptor agonists (exenatide, liraglutide, lixisenatide, albiglutide, dulaglutide, or semaglutide) published in the English language from March 2016 up to March 2024. The semaglutide effect on DR RCTs, the main target of this paper, was analyzed thoroughly. The search for available RCTs of GLP1-RA in patients with type 2 diabetes among MENA countries were included. Other non-RCT trials such as cohort studies, case-control studies, cross-sectional studies, and studies that lack retinopathy as an outcome were excluded. Moreover, trials that evaluated the use of medications off-market or not strongly recommended by the FDA were eliminated.

Data Extraction

Diabetes retinopathy outcome data were extracted independently from eligible studies by two researchers (GA) and (TH).

A coding manual was used to unify collected data. A coding manual used including patient characteristics such as demographics, duration of diabetes, background medications, average HbA1c, change in HbA1c, study characteristics including (First author name, year of publication, study design, number of patients included in the treatment group, the control

group, the medication of investigation, the medication of control, and retinopathy outcomes) and statistical characteristic including (Odds ratio of the outcome, 95% Confidence intervals). Data on diabetes retinopathy were extracted from trials of primary or secondary outcomes and/or adverse events of each trial. The Revised Cochrane risk-of-bias tool for randomized trials was used to appraise the quality of RCT by two researchers.

Data Analysis

We searched the relationship between GLP1-RA and retinopathy outcomes reported in the studies by the odds ratio (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI). We took from each study the directly reported OR and 95% CI. The pooled OR and 95%CI were calculated using the random-effect model. Heterogeneity was assessed by using the I^2 statistics. Including the RCTs only in the analysis has reduced the risk of heterogeneity. Heterogeneity is higher or greater than expected by chance alone if the I^2 statistics were $\geq 75\%$.

Ethical Consideration

This is a systematic review of published trials. Actual patients were not involved in the review. Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) approval was granted for this review with IRB approval No. E-2095.

Results

A total of 20,000 studies were identified during the databases search, and 7,435 duplicated records were removed before screening. 13,592 articles remained for an abstract review. A total of 392 were included as full-text records. Other trials were excluded due to irrelevant reported outcomes or due to the study type. Finally, a total of 12 RCTs of semaglutide were included in the analysis (Figure 1). The baseline characteristics of the studies are shown in Table 1 (Appendix). Among 12 studies with 11,854 patients included, 8 studies were centered on injectable semaglutide and 4 out of 12 studies were using oral semaglutide. The mean sample size is 985.4 patients with an average age of 59.39 years and 55.3 % male. The mean follow-up period was 52.5 weeks among 12 studies with an average duration length of diabetes of 9.33 years. Mean of HbA1c is 8.1. Three studies out of included 12 reported DR at the baseline. RCT trials investigating semaglutide effects on DR among MENA were not available searching online databases.

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow Diagram

Risk of Bias and Study Quality Assessment

Regarding the quality assessment of included RCTs, the included studies were of low risk of randomization, allocation, attrition bias, reporting bias, and any other biases (Figure 2).

Quantitative Results

In this systematic review, Semaglutide therapy was associated with a pooled effect size for retinopathy incidence of 1.12 (95% CI: 1.00-1.12). Semaglutide use has shown a non-statistically significant increase in the risk of retinopathy progression in diabetes patients among the included trials (Figure 3). Six major RCT Trials showed an increased risk of DR in this analysis. A reduction in HbA1c of 1.26% (95% CI: -1.29-1.15) in favor to semaglutide use. Heterogenicity in the result for each analysis is low.

Discussion

This systematic review includes 12 RCTs to identify the efficacy and tolerability of semaglutide compared with placebo or other antidiabetic medications. Our focus is to study the effect of semaglutide on diabetic retinopathy progression.

The SUSTAIN-6 clinical trial reported a higher rate of DR has necessitated the need for conducting several reviews to find the link association between GLP1-RA and DR among diabetes patients [7]. Reports from a few meta-analyses revealed an association of GLP1-RA with retinopathy [27]. Albiglutide was associated with an increase in DR compared to placebo [26]. An increased risk of DR associated with the use of liraglutide, semaglutide, and dulaglutide is reported [32]. Other GLP1-RA agents did not show such results

[26]. Other meta-analysis of the same outcome showed no elevated risk with semaglutide and retinopathy [11, 27]. Hu, et al meta-analysis reported results of no association between semaglutide and DR [22]. Our systematic reviews focused on semaglutide association with worsening of retinopathy progression. Our results were consistent with previous findings of metanalysis [26]. Our systematic review revealed uncertainty in determining the effect of semaglutide on diabetic retinopathy which was non-statically significant. To our knowledge, this is the first systematic review of semaglutide and DR progression in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) countries based on a search in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO). This limitation of data availability could affect in generalization of the results as diabetic retinopathy outcome should be individualized based on demographic characteristics and personal circumstances. In the included RCTs, a broad-spectrum population was included from multi-centers in different countries nevertheless a larger randomized clinical trial should be conducted with the inclusion of (the MENA) population. We found that our review has low heterogenicity and risk bias.

Limitations

It’s worthwhile to mention that semaglutide effects on retinopathy data were based on trials that DR outcomes were not the primary outcomes of semaglutide use and the need to have well-designed clinical trials to study this association.

FOCUS trial is anticipated RCT that is dedicated to semaglutide and retinopathy risk as primary outcome

might help in answering multiple concerns regarding semaglutide and possible retinopathy. Results are expected in 2026.

Another limitation is the short follow-up duration of the included trials with the longest follow-up duration being 109 weeks, thus the expected possible DR progression could not be captured. Moreover, the definition of DR in the included RCTs was not unified

which could affect the outcome results. Among selected trials, patients with DR were included in some of the trials as baseline characteristics such as SUSTAIN 6, however, other RCTs did not include such patients. These differences in the inclusion criteria could affect the measured outcome.

Figure 2: Risk of Bias Assessment

Figure 3: The Effect of Semaglutide on DR Progression
 DR: Diabetes retinopathy

Conclusion

This systematic review highlights the use of semaglutide has an uncertain effect on diabetic retinopathy progression among individuals with type 2 diabetes. We suggest more studies that cover the MENA area with consideration of the large size of the population, long duration of study, and proper baseline characteristics to measure the effect of semaglutide on the retina and to understand the possible genetic and racial causality. Clinicians are strongly recommended to have a full assessment of retina status and risk factors for patients with diabetes before considering semaglutide. Frequent retinal monitoring may be needed based on the patient clinical scenario.

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References

- [1] Simo R, Hernández C, et al. GLP-1R as a target for the treatment of diabetic retinopathy: Friend or foe? *Diabetes*. 2017 Jun;66(6):1453-1460. doi: 10.2337/db16-1474.
- [2] Nathan DM, The DCCT Research Group. The Diabetes Control and Complications Trial/Epidemiology of Diabetes Interventions and Complications Study at 30 years: Overview. *Diabetes Care*. 2014 Jan;37(1):9-16. doi: 10.2337/dc13-2112.

- [3] Stratton I, Kohner E, Aldington S, et al. UKPDS 50: Risk factors for incidence and progression of retinopathy in type II diabetes over 6 years from diagnosis. *Diabetologia*. 2001 Feb;44(2):156-163. doi: 10.1007/s001250051593.
- [4] Bien S, Klufas M, Ho A, et al. Worsening of diabetic retinopathy with rapid improvement in systemic glucose control: A review. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2019 Apr;21(2):454-466. doi: 10.1111/dom.13532.
- [5] Saw M, Wong V, Van Ho I, et al. New anti-hyperglycemic agents for type 2 diabetes and their effects on diabetic retinopathy. *Eye (Lond)*. 2019 Dec;33(12):1842-1851. doi: 10.1038/s41433-019-0481-5.
- [6] Sheahan K, Wahlberg E, Gilbert M, et al. An overview of GLP-1 agonists and recent cardiovascular outcomes trials. *Postgrad Med J*. 2020 Feb;96(1132):156-161. doi: 10.1136/postgradmedj-2019-137118.
- [7] Marso SP, Bain SC, Consoli A, Eliaschewitz FG, Jódar E, Leiter LA, et al. Semaglutide and cardiovascular outcomes in patients with type 2 diabetes. *N Engl J Med*. 2016 Nov;375(19):1834-1844. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1607141.
- [8] Albert S, Wood E, Ahir V, et al. Glucagon-like peptide 1-receptor agonists and A1c: Good for the heart but less so for the eyes? *Diabetes Metab Syndr*. 2022 Dec;17(1):102556. doi: 10.1016/j.dsx.2022.102556.
- [9] Sharma A, Parachuri N, Kumar N, et al. Semaglutide and the risk of diabetic retinopathy—current perspective. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2022 Jan;36(1):147-149. doi: 10.1111/dom.14606.
- [10] Bethel M, Diaz R, Castellana N, et al. HbA1c change and diabetic retinopathy during GLP-1 receptor agonist cardiovascular outcome trials: A meta-analysis and meta-regression. *Diabetes Care*. 2021 Feb;44(2):290-296. doi: 10.2337/dc20-1525.
- [11] Avgerinos I, Michailidis T, Liakos A, et al. Oral semaglutide for type 2 diabetes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2020 Mar;22(3):335-345. doi: 10.1111/dom.13915.
- [12] Vilsbøll T, Bain S, Leiter L, et al. Semaglutide, reduction in glycated hemoglobin, and the risk of diabetic retinopathy. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2018 Apr;20(4):889-897. doi: 10.1111/dom.13253.
- [13] Dicembrini I, Nreu B, Scatena A, et al. Microvascular effects of glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists in type 2 diabetes: A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Acta Diabetol*. 2017 Nov;54(11):933-941. doi: 10.1007/s00592-017-1027-y.
- [14] Mouhammad Z, Vohra R, Horwitz A, et al. Glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor agonists—potential game changers in the treatment of glaucoma? *Ophthalmology Times*. 2022.
- [15] Smits M, Van Raalte D, et al. Safety of semaglutide. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)*. 2021 Aug;12:748339. doi: 10.3389/fendo.2021.748339.
- [16] Trujillo J, et al. Safety and tolerability of once-weekly GLP-1 receptor agonists in type 2 diabetes. *J Clin Pharm Ther*. 2020 Sep;45(1):43-60. doi: 10.1111/jcpt.13128.
- [17] Holst J, Madsbad S, et al. Semaglutide seems to be more effective than other GLP-1RAs. *Ann Transl Med*. 2017 Dec;5(24):505. doi: 10.21037/atm.2017.11.10.
- [18] Wołos-Kłosowicz K, Matuszewski W, Rutkowska J, et al. Will GLP-1 analogues and SGLT-2 inhibitors become new game changers for diabetic retinopathy? *J Clin Med*. 2022 Oct;11(20):6183. doi: 10.3390/jcm11206183.
- [19] Linong J, Xiaolin D, Yiming L, et al. Efficacy and safety of once-weekly semaglutide versus once-daily sitagliptin as add-on to metformin in patients with type 2 diabetes in SUSTAIN China: A 30-week, double-blind, phase 3a, randomized trial. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2021 Mar;23(3):404-414. doi: 10.1111/dom.14218.
- [20] Alabdulkarim H, Bawazir O, Garcia Uranga J, et al. Once-weekly semaglutide compared to other two GLP-1RAs available in the public healthcare system in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia: A relative cost of control analysis. *Value Health*. 2019 Nov;22(Suppl 1). doi: 10.1016/j.jval.2019.09.1294.
- [21] Alfayes O, Almohammed O, Alkhezi O, et al. Network meta-analysis of once-weekly glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists: A focus on cardiovascular safety and mortality. *Diabetes*. 2020 Jan;69(Suppl 1):974-P. doi: 10.2337/db20-974-P.
- [22] Hu S, Su X, Fan G. Efficacy and tolerability of subcutaneous semaglutide for type 2 diabetes patients: An updated systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetol Metab Syndr*. 2023 Oct;15(1). Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10612199/>. doi: 10.1186/s13098-023-01035-8.
- [23] Aroda VR, et al. Effect and safety of oral semaglutide monotherapy in type 2 diabetes—PIONEER 1 trial. *Diabetes*. 2018;67(Suppl 1). doi: 10.2337/db18-2-lb.
- [24] Davies M, et al. Semaglutide 2.4 mg once a week in adults with overweight or obesity, and type 2 diabetes (STEP 2): A randomised, double-blind, double-dummy, placebo-controlled, phase 3 trial. *Lancet*. 2021;397(10278):971–984. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00213-0.
- [25] Kaku K, et al. Safety and efficacy of once-weekly semaglutide vs additional oral antidiabetic drugs in Japanese people with inadequately controlled type 2 diabetes: A randomized trial. *Diabetes Obes Metab*. 2018;20(5):1202–1212. doi: 10.1111/dom.13218.

- [26] Kapoor I, et al. GLP-1 receptor agonists and diabetic retinopathy: A meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials. *Surv Ophthalmol*. 2023;68(6):1071–1083. doi: 10.1016/j.survophthal.2023.07.002.
- [27] Malyszczak A, et al. Novel antidiabetic drugs and the risk of diabetic retinopathy: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *J Clin Med*. 2024;13(6):1797.
- [28] Rodbard H, et al. Oral semaglutide versus empagliflozin in patients with type 2 diabetes uncontrolled on metformin: The PIONEER 2 trial. *Diabetes*. 2019;68(Suppl 1). doi: 10.2337/db19-54-or.
- [29] Mosenzon O, et al. Efficacy and safety of oral semaglutide in patients with type 2 diabetes and moderate renal impairment (PIONEER 5): A placebo-controlled, randomised, phase 3a trial. *Diabetes*. 2019;68(Suppl 1). doi: 10.2337/db19-1004-p.
- [30] Rodbard HW, et al. Semaglutide added to basal insulin in type 2 diabetes (SUSTAIN 5): A randomized, controlled trial. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2018;103(6):2291–2301. doi: 10.1210/jc.2018-00070.
- [31] Rosenstock J, et al. Effect of additional oral semaglutide vs sitagliptin on glycosylated hemoglobin in adults with type 2 diabetes uncontrolled with metformin alone or with sulfonylurea. *JAMA*. 2019;321(15):1466. doi: 10.1001/jama.2019.2942.
- [32] Yoshida Y, et al. Progression of retinopathy with glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists with cardiovascular benefits in type 2 diabetes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Diabetes Complications*. 2022;36(8):108255. doi: 10.1016/j.jdiacomp.2022.108255.
- [33] Zinman B, et al. Semaglutide once weekly as add-on to SGLT-2 inhibitor therapy in type 2 diabetes (SUSTAIN 9): A randomised, placebo-controlled trial. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol*. 2019;7(5):356–367. doi: 10.1016/S2213-8587(19)30066-X.
- [34] Seino Y, Terauchi Y, Osonoi T, et al. Safety and efficacy of semaglutide once weekly vs sitagliptin once daily, both as monotherapy in Japanese people with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Obes Metab* [Internet]. 2018;20(2):378–88. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28786547>.
- [35] Pieber TR, Bode B, Mertens A, et al. Efficacy and safety of oral semaglutide with flexible dose adjustment versus sitagliptin in type 2 diabetes (PIONEER 7): A multicentre, open-label, randomised, phase 3a trial. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol*. 2019 Jul;7(7):528–39.
- [36] Zinman B, Aroda VR, Buse JB, et al. Efficacy, safety, and tolerability of oral semaglutide versus placebo added to insulin ± metformin in patients with type 2 diabetes: The PIONEER 8 trial. *Diabetes Care*. 2019 Sep 17;42(12):2262–71.

Appendix

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics and Summary of Trials Included in the Review

First Author /Year	Intervention	Control	Baseline insulin %	Age(Year)	Male(%)	Follow-up duration in	Number of patients	No. Pt in intervention	No. Pt in control	Duration of diabetes In years	Mean HbA1C	Baseline DR	Reported risk	Retinopathy outcomes in Tx Group	Retinopathy outcomes in control group
Marso,2016	semaglutide	Placebo	58%	64.6	60.7	109	3297	1648	1649	13.9	8.70%	66%	OR:1.75	50/1648	29/1649
Senio,2017	semaglutide	Sitagliptin	0	58.3	76.3	30	308	205	103	8	8.1%%	0%	OR:0.75	2/102.	4/103
Kaku, 2018	semaglutide	OHA	0	60	50	63	600	480	120	8.8	8.10%	0	OR:1.13	16/241.	6/120
J.Rosenstock,2019	Semaglutide	Sitagliptin	17%	58	52.8	78	1861	1395	466	8.6	8.3	33.1	OR:0.82	17/465	29/467
B. Zinman,2019	Semaglutide	Placebo	0%	57	58.3	26	301	150	151	9.7	8	38	OR: 0.40	3/151	10/151
H. Rodbard,2019	Semaglutide	Empagliflozin	0	58	50.5	52	819	412	410	7.4	8.1	0	OR:3.32	14/412	5/410
M. Davies,2021	Semaglutide	Placebo	0.20%	55	49.1	69	1210	805	402	8	8.1	0	OR:1.20	11/403	11/403
B. Zinman,2019	Semaglutide	Placebo	20%	61	54	52	731	547	184	3.5	8	0	OR:1.32	9/181	8/184
V. Aroda,2019	Semaglutide	Placebo	0	55	50.8	20	703	525	178	8	8.1	0	OR:0.92	2/175.	3/178
T. Pieber ,2019	Semaglutide	Sitagliptin	0%	57	57	52	504	253	250	8.8	8.3	0	OR:0.99	6\253	6\251
O. Mosenzon,2019	Semaglutide	Placebo	20%	70	48	24	324	163	160	14	8	0	OR:2.21	5\163	2\161
H. Rodbard ,2018	Semaglutide	Placebo	100%	58.8	56.1	30	397	263	133	13.3	8.4	0%	OR:5.68	0.8\133	0\133

